
Final report

Bando young researcher

Piattaforma digitale per E-health

Introduction:

The spread of wearable technology, including heart rate monitors, glucometers, and smartwatches, has changed personal health management. By integrating these devices with mobile applications, continuous and non-invasive health monitoring can now be conducted outside traditional clinical settings. These tools provide a comprehensive, real-time overview of an individual's physiological well-being. This project aims to develop a centralized platform designed to aggregate, visualize, and analyze data from various sources alongside qualitative data from web forms, creating a personalized health database accessible to both users and healthcare providers for remote assistance. An example of application of the platform is the early identification of prediabetes in youth with obesity. Specifically, using wearable technology for this purpose can be used for preventing long-term progression to type 2 diabetes (T2D). Standard diagnostic criteria rely on HbA1c, fasting plasma glucose (FPG), and the 2-hour oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT). However, these tests face several challenges. They show poor reproducibility due to preanalytical and analytical variability, and the OGTT requires overnight fasting, is time-consuming, expensive, and often poorly tolerated by children, causing nausea. A wearable device such as the Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) offers a promising way to record comprehensive glucose profiles in free-living conditions.

Aim of the project

The project involves creating a centralized system for the collection, visualization, and analysis of data from various wearable devices, including smartwatches, continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) sensors, smartbands, and fitness trackers, as well as web forms and questionnaires. This platform will allow

researchers to easily and effectively gather diverse data, such as glucose metabolism metrics, physical activity levels (step counts, heart rate, and energy expenditure), dietary habits, and estimated nutritional content of meals, alongside user attitudes, feelings, experiences, and opinions.

Results

The platform design

The platform designed for managing research participants or clinical study datashow has the following key sections: “Dashboard”, “Participants”, “Data Monitor”, “Charts”, “Download Data”. In the Participants section, we have a full list of participant, where each record includes a unique identification code, the participant's gender, their active status, and any associated study groups. In the Data Monitor section, the platform displays the current status of data synchronization or file uploads for each participant. In the Charts section, the collected data can be visualized, as shown in Figure 1. In the Charts section, the user can select either a record meal or a recorded workout and the platform will display a meal/workout summary, including glucose, heart rate, and meal/workout indicators. In Figure 2, an example of a meal summary is shown, as well as zooming in the increase in blood glucose levels during the meal. In Figure 3, an example of a workout summary is shown, displaying that it is a strength training session, with a duration of 72.23 minutes and a decrease in blood glucose levels during the activity.

Specifically, it is possible to select participant and filter based on date inputs for specific time ranges, and various data categories including Dialogs, Workouts, Meals, Heartrate, Calories Active, Distance, Steps, Respiratory Rate, HRV, Blood Oxygen, and Hypnogram. In the Download Data section, it is possible to select a participant and download their data.

Figure 1: Charts section within the web-based platform

Figure 2: An example of a meal summary within the Charts section

Figure 3: An example of a meal summary within the Charts section

The clinical study

Along with the development of the platform, we organized a cross-sectional study aiming at determining if metrics collected via a wearable device can aid in identifying prediabetes in youths with obesity, offering complementary insights to traditional diagnostic methods. This cross-sectional study analyzing CGM metrics as predictors of PD in youths with obesity with a stratification into clinically distinct groups resulted in three main findings: 1) youths with PD spent significantly less time in tight glucose ranges (70-140 mg/dL and 70-120 mg/dL) compared to those with normoglycemia; 2) time in tight glucose ranges emerged the most accurate metric for identifying PD in our pediatric cohort ; 3) in youths with PD, time in tight glucose ranges and GV indices were significantly associated with glucose levels during OGTT, with distinct correlations observed between youths with IGT and those with IFG.

Study design

In collaboration with the University of Verona, we recruited Caucasian youth with obesity ($\$BMI > 2\$ SD$) from three Italian university hospitals in Verona, Chieti, and Messina. Participants were excluded if they had type 2 diabetes, genetic or endocrine causes of obesity, or were taking medications that influence weight or glucose levels.

During clinical examinations, weight, height, BMI, and waist circumference were recorded using standardized procedures. To monitor glucose levels, participants wore an Abbott FreeStyle Libre® 2 sensor for two weeks. Within the first eight days of this monitoring period, patients underwent blood tests for HbA1c and a standard OGTT performed at 8:00 a.m. after an overnight fast. In cases where scheduling conflicts or illness delayed the OGTT, it was completed within one month of the sensor-wearing period to ensure data consistency.

Blood samples were taken at baseline and at times +30, +60, +90, and +120 minutes to measure plasma glucose. Plasma glucose was analyzed using standard procedures at the central laboratories of the three participating Centers. Additionally, area under the curve (AUC) of glucose values measured during OGTT were calculated by the trapezoidal rule.

According to current guidelines, PD was defined if participants satisfy any, or a combination, of the following criteria: 1) an HbA1c of 5.7% to 6.4% (39 to 47 mmol/mol); 2) venous fasting glucose of 100 to 125 mg/dl (5.6 to 6.9 mmol/l) indicating IFG; and 3) 2-h glucose (2-h PG) value during a 75-g OGTT of 140 to 199 mg/dL (7.8 to 11.0 mmol/l) indicating IGT (3,5). Participants not meeting the diagnostic criteria for PD were defined as having “normoglycemia”.

The CGM readings from the first day were excluded from the analysis, given that issues with less accurate measures are known to occur on the day of CGM placement with the devices used. At least four full days (96 h) of evaluable CGM data were required for the analysis.

The following CGM metrics were computed: mean glucose (MG), glucose management indicator (GMI), percentage of time in range 70 -180 mg/dl (3.9-10 mmol/L) (TIR), T1R 70-140 mg/dL and 70-120 mg/dL, T2R > 140 mg/dL and 120 mg/dL, time in hyperglycemia 181-250 mg/dl (10-13.9 mmol/L) (level 1 hyperglycaemia) (TAR1) and above 250 mg/dl (13.9 mmol/L) (level 2 hyperglycaemia) (TAR2), time below 70 mg/dL (3.9 mmol/L) (TBR), time in hypoglycemia 54-70 mg/dl (3.0 - 3.9 mmol/L) (level 1 hypoglycaemia) (TBR1) and below 54 mg/dl (3.0 mmol/L) (level 2 hypoglycaemia) (TBR2), and glycemic variability (GV) measures, such as SD and the coefficient of variation (CV).

The following additional GV metrics were also included in the analysis:

- mean of daily differences (MODD), which is calculated as the mean of the absolute differences between glucose values at the same time on consecutive days (16)

- mean amplitude of glycemic excursion (MAGE), which is an arithmetic average of either the upward or downward of all glycemic excursions exceeding the SD obtained within a 24-hour period (17);
- J INDEX, which is calculated as $0.324 \times (MG + SD)^2$ (18);
- continuous overall net glycemic action (CONGA), which is calculated as the standard deviation of the differences between glucose values measured at 1-hour time intervals (19);
- glycemic risk assessment in diabetes equation (GRADE), which is calculated as the median of the distribution whose samples are computed according to $425 \times \{\log[\log(G)] + 0.16\}^2$ where G represents a sample of glucose measurement (20).

The primary analysis assessed the statistical difference in the CGM-derived metrics between participants defined as normoglycemic and those with PD, as defined by the ADA and ISPAD criteria (3,5). The paired-data comparison was performed by non-parametric Wilcoxon signed rank test. A p-value (p) < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Spearman correlation coefficients between CGM-derived metrics and OGTT-derived metrics were calculated in both normoglycemic and PD groups. Moreover, in the PD group, correlation analysis was separately assessed for participants with IGT, whether diagnosed solely by IGT or in combination with IFG and/or HbA1c criteria, and those with IFG, whether diagnosed solely or in combination with HbA1c criteria.

The secondary analysis tested the independent association between PD and CGM-derived metrics, adjusting for potential confounders by using binary logistic regression analyses, with PD as dependent variable and CGM-derived metrics as independent ones. The k-fold cross-validation approach was applied to estimate the predictive accuracy of the classification model. The dataset was divided into non-overlapping $k = 10$ equal folds. For the k^{th} part, we train the classifier to the other $K-1$ parts of the data and calculate the performance of the identified model when predicting the k^{th} part of the data (21). Classification performance was assessed using True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR), which measure the proportion of positives that are correctly classified and positives that are wrongly classified, respectively and are defined as follows: $TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$, and $FPR = \frac{FP}{TN+FP}$

Defining the Receiver Operator Characteristic (ROC) as the curve describing the relation between TPR and FPR, the performance of the classifiers is also evaluated through the Area Under the ROC Curve (AUROC), which is calculated by the trapezoidal rule. Classifiers with AUROC value significantly above 0.5

achieve good performance, while AUROC equal to 0.5 means that the classifier behaves exactly as a random variable (22).

The glycemic variability measures, including MODD, MAGE, J-INDEX, CONGA, GRADE, were calculated with EasyGV software v10, while CGM metrics, including SD, CV, GMI, TIR, TATR > 140 mg/dL, TATR > 120 mg/dL, TAR1, TAR2, TBR, TBR1, TBR2, were calculated with Matlab 2022a. Additionally, data processing and statistical analyses were also performed in MATLAB 2022a.

Characteristics of the Study Population According to Prediabetes Status

Of the 94 participants from whom data were collected, 84 met the criteria for the minimum required CGM wear time and were included in the analysis. Characteristics of the overall study population and according to PD status are shown in Table 1. Age, sex, BMI and BMI Z-score were similar between participants with normoglycemia and those with PD. As expected, HbA1c and glucose values measured during OGTT were higher in the PD group. Compared to participants with normoglycemia, participants with PD spent significantly lower percentages in TIR 70-140 mg/dL (median 96.4% vs 98.1%, $p=0.03$) and TIR 70-120 mg/dL (median 91.1% vs. 91.9%, $p=0.02$). Moreover, participants with PD showed a higher median of the frequency distribution for all glucose values in the timeframe 8 AM- 10 AM (G_{pp-b}^{50}). No significant differences were found in the other CGM metrics.

Correlation analysis

The results of the correlation analysis between CGM metrics and OGTT glucose values are presented in Supplementary Tables 3-6, while a subset of the most significant correlations is shown in Figure 1.

In the normoglycemic group (Figure 1A), no significant correlations were observed between any CGM metrics and OGTT glucose values. In the PD group (Figure 1B), GV metrics, particularly SD and CV, showed positive correlations with glucose levels measured at 30 and 60 minutes during the OGTT (SD: $r=0.31$, $p=0.03$; CV: $r=0.31$, $p=0.03$). Additionally, both SD and MODD were positively correlated with AUC of glucose during OGTT (SD: $r=.030$, $p=0.04$; MODD: $r=0.30$, $p=0.04$), while MODD also correlated with glucose values measured at time 60 minutes ($r=.037$, $p<0.01$). In participants with IFG (Figure 1C), both TIR metrics were negatively correlated with FPG (TIR 70-140 mg/dL : $r=-0.44$, $p=0.02$; TIR 70-120 mg/dL : $r=-0.40$, $p<0.01$) and MODD was positively correlated with FPG ($r=0.39$, $p=0.03$). In participants with IGT (Figure 1D), GV metrics, including SD, CV, MAGE and MODD, showed strong positive correlations

with glucose values at time 120 minutes during the OGTT (SD:r=0.60, $p < 0.01$; CV:r=0.65, $p < 0.01$; MAGE:r=0.56, $p < 0.01$; MODD:r=0.67, $p < 0.01$). Additionally, MODD was also positively correlated with glucose values at 60 minutes ($r = 0.057$, $p < 0.01$) and OGTT glucose AUC ($r = 0.061$, $p < 0.01$). TITR 70-140 mg/dL and TITR 70-120 mg/dL were negatively correlated with OGTT glucose AUC (TITR 70-140 mg/dL:r=-0.53, $p=0.02$; TITR70-120 mg/dL :r=-0.52, $p=0.03$). Finally, TITR 70-140 mg/dL was inversely correlated with 120-minute glucose levels ($r = -0.61$, $p < 0.01$). None of the other CGM metrics showed significant correlations with OGTT-derived indices across all four groups.

Logistic regression analysis

We conduct a proof-of-concept analysis to assess whether CGM metrics can predict a PD diagnosis. Binary logistic regression analysis identified %TITR 70-140 mg/dL, %TITR 70-120 mg/dL, and %TATR > 140 mg/dL as significant indicators for diagnosing PD with p -value < 0.05 , as shown in Table 2 and in Supplementary Figure 2 and 3. Among the three covariates, %TATR > 140 mg/dL exhibits the highest odds ratio, indicating a stronger association with the likelihood of diagnosing PD.

In contrast, %TITR 70-140 mg/dL and %TITR 70-120 mg/dL achieve higher TPR than %TATR > 140 mg/dL (0.40 versus 0.50 and 0.60, respectively) and lower FPR (0.39 versus 0.37 and 0.33, respectively) resulting in higher AUROC scores (0.58 versus 0.62 and 0.64).

As reported in Table 2, CV and MODD show the two highest odds ratios, 118.03 and 19.49, respectively. While these values may suggest a strong positive association with the model output, such a high ratio can be attributed to overfitting, as indicated by p -values greater than 0.05 and an AUROC score close to 0.50, which means that the models are randomly guessing the output. Finally, TBR, STD, MG and MAGE are not suitable for diagnosing PD, as the AUROC is close to or below 0.50, indicating poor discriminatory ability of these covariates.

Additionally, the analysis was repeated with age incorporated as an additional covariate in the regression model. For TITR 70-140 mg/dL, TITR 70-120 mg/dL, and TATR >140 mg/dL, the coefficient associated with the age covariate was not statistically significant, with p -values of 0.20, 0.25, and 0.17, respectively and corresponding AUROC scores of 0.60, 0.61, and 0.55. Finally, the analysis was repeated including also sex as an additional covariate, and the results were similar to those obtained when age was added suggesting that the inclusion of age and sex does not enhance the model's discriminatory performance.

Supplementary Table 7 showed the results of logistic regression analysis performed considering the additional CGM metrics measuring glucose concentrations during fasting and postprandial time windows. None of these additional CGM metrics were identified as significant indicators for diagnosing PD, except for the median of the frequency distribution for all glucose values in the timeframe 8 AM- 10 AM (G^{50}_{pp-b}). This metric showed similar AUROC to TITR 70-140 mg/dL and TITR 70-120 mg/dL, however its TPR and FPR were significantly lower compared the ones found for TITR metrics.

Table 1. Characteristics of the overall study population and according to prediabetes status. The significant p-values are highlighted in italics.

Characteristic	Normal glucose tolerance (n=35)	Prediabetes (n=49)	p-value	Overall (n=84)
Age [years]	13.30 (11.10-15.50)	12.50 (11.40-13.80)	0.22	12.90 (11.40-14.50)
Gender				
Male [n(%)]	20 (57.10)	26(53.00)	0.71	46 (54.70)
Female [n (%)]	15 (42.90)	23(47.00)		38 (45.30)
BMI [kg/m ²]	30.90 (29.40-36.20)	32.00 (28.70-35.50)	0.80	31.70 (28.80-35.80)
BMI Z score	3.20 (2.80-3.56)	3.08 (2.75-3.32)	0.14	3.11 (2.74-3.45)
HbA1c [%]	5.40 (5.35-5.50)	5.70 (5.40-5.80)	<i><0.001</i>	5.50 (5.40-5.70)
Fasting plasma glucose [mg/dL]	92.00 (87.00-95.10)	102.00 (99.00-109.50)	<i><0.001</i>	97.5 (91.0-103.5)
plasma glucose at t= 30 mins [mg/dL]	133.00 (118.50-144.70)	149.00 (135.50-164.00)	<i><0.001</i>	142.00 (127.20-158.50)
plasma glucose at t= 60 mins [mg/dL]	127.00 (105.00-136.00)	128.50 (118.00-141.00)	0.18	128.50 (114.00-141.00)
plasma glucose at t= 90 mins [mg/dL]	109.00 (100.50-128.50)	126.00 (112.00-140.20)	<i>0.02</i>	124.00 (106.20-136.00)
plasma glucose at t= 120 mins,[mg/dL]	110.00 (100.50-120.50)	130.00 (116.70-148.00)	<i><0.001</i>	120.50 (108.00-136.00)
AUC plasma glucose [mg/dL]	117.50 (109.00-127.70)	131.90 (120.30-141.50)	<i><0.001</i>	126.50 (113.60-136.30)
CGM use [%]	84.20	92.90	0.91	88.90

	(59.90-100.00)	(81.20-100.00)		(65.80-100.00)
MG [mg/dL]	98.90 (96.20-104.10)	100.30 (95.20-106.70)	0.29	100.20 (95.60-105.80)
TBR	0.66 (0.13-2.08)	0.49 (0.00-1.80)	0.49	0.70 (0.10-2.33)
TBR1	0.56 (0.22-1.45)	0.45 (0.00-1.31)	0.32	0.61 (0.17-2.14)
TIR	99.30 (97.80-99.80)	99.50 (98.00-99.90)	0.16	99.20 (97.60-99.80)
TITR 70-140 mg/dL	98.10 (96.20-99.20)	96.40 (93.80-98.50)	0.03	96.93 (94.90-99.10)
TITR 70-120 mg/dL	91.90 (85.70-95.80)	91.10 (84.20-93.20)	0.02	91.0 (83.80-93.80)
TATR > 120 mg/dL	7.50 (3.12-11.86)	7.66 (4.15-14.52)	0.08	7.86 (4.12-14.74)
TATR > 140 mg/dL	0.83 (0.19-1.56)	0.93 (0.13-2.40)	0.07	1.05 (0.22-2.65)
CV	13.00 (11.00-15.00)	14.00 (12.00-16.00)	0.05	14.00 (12.00-15.00)
SD [mg/dL]	13.50 (11.00-15.00)	13.70 (12.4-16.8)	0.10	13.70 (12.1-15.8)
MODD	0.73 (0.60-0.83)	0.78 (0.67-0.80)	0.08	0.76 (0.62-0.86)
MAGE	25.00 (20.9-29.4)	25.3 (22.70-28.90)	0.40	25.20 (22.30-29.50)
J INDEX	13.10 (11.60-14.10)	13.00 (12.10-15.10)	0.34	13.0 (11.70-14.80)
CONGA	5.03 (4.85-5.27)	5.08 (4.78-5.51)	0.48	5.07 (4.85-5.35)
GRADE	$1.20 \cdot 10^3$ ($1.19 \cdot 10^3$ - $1.2 \cdot 10^3$)	$1.20 \cdot 10^3$ ($1.18 \cdot 10^3$ - $1.21 \cdot 10^3$)	0.29	$1.20 \cdot 10^3$ ($1.19 \cdot 10^3$ - $1.22 \cdot 10^3$)

Data are presented as median (IQR), except for sex distribution.

Abbreviations: MG, mean glucose; TBR, percentage of time below range <70 mg/dL (3.9 mmol/L); TBR1, percentage of time within range 70-54 mg/dL (3.9-3 mmol/L); TIR, percentage of time in range 70-180 mg/dL (3.9-10.0 mmol/L); TITR percentage of time in tight range ; TATR, percentage of time above tight range ; CV, coefficient of glucose variation; SD, standard deviation of glucose; MODD, mean of daily differences; MAGE, mean amplitude of glycemic excursion; CONGA, continuous overall net glycemic action; GRADE, glycemic risk assessment in diabetes equation.

The following metrics were not reported because their values were zero in both the normal glucose tolerance and prediabetes groups: TBR2, percentage of time below <54 mg/dL (3.0 mmol/L); TAR, percentage of time above >180 mg/dL (10.1 mmol/L); TAR1, percentage of time within range 181-250 mg/dL (10.1-13.9 mmol/L); TAR2, percentage of time above >250 mg/dL (13.9 mmol/L).

Figure 1: Spearman correlation coefficients between a sub-set of CGM metrics and OGTT indices for normoglycemic (a), prediabetes (b), impaired fasting glucose (IFG) (c) and impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) (d) groups. The sample size is reported for each subtable. The color bar represents the strength and direction of correlations between CGM-derived metrics and OGTT-derived values, ranging from -1 (in blue) to 1 (in red).

Abbreviations: MG, mean glucose; TITR, time in tight range; TATR, time above tight range; CV, coefficient of glucose variation; SD, standard deviation of glucose; MAGE, mean amplitude of glycemic excursion; MODD, mean of daily differences; G_i, plasma glucose at t= i mins, with i=0, 30, 60, 90, 120; AUC, area under the curve of plasma glucose.

*p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001.

Table 2: Logistic regression model estimates, along with their odds ratio, standard error and p-value. True positive rate, false positive rate and area under the curve of the receiving operating curve (AUROC) were calculated using cross-validation. The significant p-values are highlighted in italics.

Regressors	Estimate	Odds Ratio	Standard error	p-value	True positive Rate	False Positive Rate	AUROC
MG	0.03	1.03	0.03	0.31	0.25	0.41	0.41
TITR 70-140 mg/dL	-0.22	0.80	0.09	<i>0.02</i>	0.50	0.37	0.62
TITR 70-120 mg/dL	-0.09	0.91	0.04	<i>0.02</i>	0.60	0.33	0.64
TATR > 140 mg/dL	0.41	1.50	0.18	<i>0.03</i>	0.40	0.39	0.58
CV	17.99	118.03	9.55	0.08	0.45	0.40	0.56
STD	0.17	1.18	0.09	0.06	0.53	0.38	0.59
MODD	2.97	19.49	1.59	0.07	0.51	0.36	0.56
MAGE	0.04	1.04	0.04	0.29	0.50	0.40	0.43

Abbreviations: MG, mean glucose; TITR, time in tight range; TATR, time above tight range; CV, coefficient of glucose variation; STD, standard deviation of glucose; MODD, mean of daily differences; MAGE, mean amplitude of glycemic excursion.